

Huddling and tail-dipping: two previously unknown behaviours of the slug *Megapallifera mutabilis* (Philomycidae)

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Abstract. We report the behaviours of the North American philomycid slug *Megapallifera mutabilis* (Hubricht, 1951) in the wild and in the laboratory. In their forest habitat during suitable weather the slugs climbed trees to feed on the algae coating the bark and took refuge in water-filled tree holes. Inside the holes two or more resting slugs were often in physical contact with each other (huddling). Slugs were also observed dipping their tails into water. Our measurements indicated that slugs foraging on tree trunks tended to lose water and tail-dipping helped dehydrated slugs absorb water. Huddling has been previously reported for other slug species, but the exact functions of the behaviour remain unknown.

ZooBank identifier. urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:0DCD402D-BFC5-4CA5-AFE7-0C874531E771

DOI. <https://doi.org/10.61733/jconch/4556>

INTRODUCTION

There are three philomycid slug genera in North America: *Philomycus* Rafinesque, 1820, *Megapallifera* Hubricht, 1956, and *Pallifera* Morse, 1864 (Fairbanks 1990). *Pallifera* species are relatively small (adults up to about 30 mm in length). In comparison, the slugs in the genera *Philomycus* and *Megapallifera* are larger (adults up to 100 mm or longer in length). There are three species in *Megapallifera* (Fairbanks 1990): *M. mutabilis* (Hubricht, 1951), *M. wetherbyi* (W.G. Binney, 1874), and *M. ragsdalei* (Webb, 1950). Of these, *M. mutabilis* is endemic to and widespread in eastern North America having been recorded from more than 15 states, including Maryland (Hubricht 1985; Paustian *et al.* 2013).

As animals with moist, permeable skin, slugs lose water from their bodies when they are exposed to a dry environment. They additionally lose water in the mucus that they deposit from the sole of their foot as they crawl. Water balance is a major determinant of gastropod activity (Machin 1975; Prior 1985), which often means their activities are limited to nighttime, cooler weather and periods of precipitation and may be guided by moisture-seeking behaviours. Published data on *M. mutabilis* are limited to a brief description of its habitat (Hubricht 1985) and microhabitat and food preferences (Paustian & Barbosa 2012). However,

water-management behaviours of the species, especially in its habitat, have not been studied.

We present here anatomical studies and field observations of *M. mutabilis* and experimental data collected with captive slugs. Our findings confirm the identity of *M. mutabilis*, demonstrate its association with the trees in its habitat, and cover various aspects of its behaviour, especially in relation to water loss and uptake.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data were collected mainly during 2006–2011 followed by occasional observations until 2024 in Black Hill Regional Park, Montgomery County, Maryland, USA (39.200°N, 077.278°W). Specimens were collected under a permit issued by the park manager (dated 18 February 1997).

Species of *Philomycus* and *Megapallifera* resemble each other externally, and the assignment of a specimen to the correct genus may require dissection: a dart sac is present in *Philomycus* but absent in *Megapallifera*. Fairbanks (1990) presented the most recent morphological and anatomical comparison of the three species in *Megapallifera*. To identify the species we are studying, we have compared the external appearances and the anatomy of our specimens with the findings of Fairbanks (1990). According to Fairbanks

(1990), overall anatomy of the genitalia of the three *Megapallifera* species were similar, but there were interspecific differences in the absolute lengths of some organs. We do not think that these differences can be relied on to differentiate species, because the ranges of the measurements of individual organs were wide and they were obtained from small numbers of specimens (two or three) that also differed in their body lengths (Fairbanks 1990). Nevertheless, we give the measurements of some organs of our specimens to allow for the dimensional comparison of different organs. The dimensions given in parentheses after the individual organs of dissected slugs are the means of measurements obtained from three slugs. These are approximate values, because the organs were naturally twisted and bent, which made it difficult to measure their lengths accurately, and attempts at straightening them out caused them to stretch, introducing additional errors. What could be called the vagina, the extremely short section of the female genitalia between the atrium and the point of bifurcation of the duct of the bursa copulatrix and the free oviduct, was especially difficult to delineate and measure. In the descriptions of genitalia, the term distal is relative to the ovotestis.

Captive slugs were kept in small plastic containers that contained wet paper towels and small dishes of water. The inner walls of the containers were also sprayed with water. Pieces of beech bark covered with algae were placed in the containers to provide food for the slugs.

To determine whether slugs lost water while feeding on trees, Experiment 1 was performed in May 2009. On different days a total of 38 slugs were removed from the trunks of trees (but not from tree holes). Each slug was weighed in the field using a digital pocket scale. The slugs were then brought to the laboratory where each slug was placed in a separate container with a small vial of water. Some of the containers were lined with wet paper. Thirty-two slugs were dropped into water and six were placed on wet paper. No food was given. Slugs were kept in the presence of water for different periods before each one was weighed again. Results are given as percent weight changes from initial field weights.

Experiment 2 was performed to test whether slugs successfully countered water loss with water contact behavior in the laboratory. Twelve slugs were removed from wet containers, weighed and then placed in dry containers for three to five hours under ambient conditions (temperature, 17-19 °C; relative humidity, 30%-40%). Afterwards, they were weighed again. Two slugs that had lost less than 5% of their initial weight during dehydration and one slug that could not be weighed on time were excluded from further consideration. Each of the remaining nine slugs that had lost

more than 5% of their body weights was placed on a small lid, which was then placed upside down on a container partially filled with water. We waited for each slug first, to contact water and then, to remain in contact with water for up to 5 hours and 40 minutes before we weighed it again. The results of both Experiment 1 and 2 were plotted as percent weight changes of slugs from dehydrated weights versus the durations of rehydration and analyzed using ordinary least squares. The statistics given are r^2 (Pearson's correlation coefficient squared) and p (probability that there is no correlation).

One dissected (CM125356) and two intact (CM125357, CM125358) *M. mutabilis* specimens in alcohol have been deposited in the Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania.

RESULTS

Identification of the slugs

Live slugs had translucent grey mantles covered with dark-grey, vaguely delineated spots (Fig. 1). Sometimes large patches of the mantle where the underlying organs were showing through acquired a tan colour (Fig. 1C). Fairbanks (1990) noted that the spots on the mantles of both *M. wetherbyi* and *M. ragsdalei* formed "broad distinct chevrons", while those on *M. mutabilis* occasionally produced "vague chevrons". The dark-grey spots on the mantles of our specimens were usually elongated and sometimes formed a pair of longitudinal rows on the dorsal mantle, but patterns that could be called chevrons were not present. The grey spots united to form a dark longitudinal band along each side of the mantle just above the sole. The sole was cream-coloured (Fig. 1D).

We dissected five specimens (Fig. 2A). The crawling lengths of the dissected slugs were between 50 and 70 mm. None had a dart sac, thus placing them in *Megapallifera*. The genital opening led into an atrium at the opposite end of which the penis and the vagina opened. The inside of the atrium was taken up mostly by two large lobes attached to the inside wall near the openings of the penis and the vagina. The penis twisted and folded over itself. The proximal end of the penis was bulbous, forming the apical chamber referred to by Fairbanks (1990). The retractor muscle of the penis and the vas deferens attached next to each other at the proximal end of the penis. The retractor muscle of the penis was long, and its proximal end formed a membranous connection to the retractor of the left tentacle (Fig. 2A). The inside of the apical chamber contained a circular structure surrounding a multi-lobed formation (Fig. 2B). The walls of the middle

Figure 1. Different individuals of *Megapallifera mutabilis* on beech trees. Photographs taken at different magnifications were rescaled for this figure. The longest and the shortest slugs, 75 mm and 45 mm, respectively, are in panel A.

Figure 2. Genitalia of *Megapallifera mutabilis*. **A**, distal organs, including the retractor of the left tentacle to which the retractor of penis was attached. **B**, inside of the penis. Abbreviations: ac, apical chamber; at, atrium; bc, bursa copulatrix; fo, free oviduct; pe, penis; rp, retractor of penis; lt, left tentacle; va, vagina; vd, vas deferens.

section of the penis were covered with large papillae that formed five or six longitudinal pilasters extending towards the distal end. Near the distal end the pilasters were replaced by irregular rows of papillae. The vagina was extremely short (0.3 mm). The duct of the bursa copulatrix (7.4 mm) was slightly shorter than the free oviduct (8.3 mm), but longer than the penis (4.6 mm). The general characteristics of the genitalia of these slugs agree with the anatomy of *M. mutabilis* as reported by Fairbanks (1990), although he did not mention the multi-lobed circular formations present in the apical chambers of our specimens (Fig. 2B).

The mantle colours and patterns of the slugs we studied and the general agreement of the anatomy of our specimens with that of *M. mutabilis* led us to identify our specimens as that species. An additional relevant piece of evidence is that *M. ragsdalei* and *M. wetherbyi* were both historically found some distance away from the state of Maryland (Hubricht 1985).

Association of *Megapallifera mutabilis* with trees

The habitat of *M. mutabilis* was a second-growth forest dominated by beech (*Fagus grandifolia* Ehrh.), tulip poplar (*Liriodendron tulipifera* L.), and oak (several *Quercus* L. species)

trees. During the months of March through early November in the mornings, following evening rains or when the humidity was high, we observed individuals of *M. mutabilis* on the trunks of trees. Most of our observations and collections were of the slugs on beech trees. We could visually identify as *M. mutabilis* the slugs on beech trees that were as high as ~4 m above the ground (higher slugs could not be identified definitively from the ground). From spring through fall *M. mutabilis* were also found in two types of refuges. The first type were cavities among exposed tree roots containing a decomposing mixture of damp tree leaves and other plant material. The second type were holes in the trunks of trees filled with rainwater and sometimes containing wind-blown tree leaves and other plant debris. Over the years we saw *M. mutabilis* in holes in the trunks of at least seven individual trees; five of which were beeches.

We monitored two tree holes (selected because they were close to a park entrance) at irregular intervals for a period of longer than 18 years. Both holes were discovered in April 2006 and last examined in November 2024; during the intervening years neither their appearances nor dimensions changed significantly (Fig. 3). The first hole was an enclosure with an open top between the main trunk and a narrower side trunk of a beech (Fig. 3A, B). The bottom of the enclosure was ~120 cm above the ground, the width of its front opening was ~4 cm and the extension of the enclosure into the trunk from the opening was ~15 cm. *Megapallifera mutabilis* were seen in this hole in April and May 2006, July 2007, May and September 2008, April and October 2009, as well as the last time it was examined in November 2024. The second tree hole was a narrow opening in another beech (Fig. 3C, D). The bottom of the enclosure was ~105 cm above the ground, the width of the opening was 2–3 cm, the height was ~7 cm and the extension of the enclosure into the trunk from the opening was ~8 cm. *Megapallifera mutabilis* were seen in this hole in April and May 2006, July 2007, May, September, October and early November 2008, March, July and October 2009 as well as the last time it was examined in November 2024. Both tree holes were also checked on several occasions in late November, December, and January during 2007–2010, but no slugs were seen in them.

Huddling and tail-dipping in tree holes

The number of slugs present in a tree hole on a single occasion varied; we saw as many as 12 *M. mutabilis* in a single hole. Besides large adults, juveniles were also seen in tree holes. The slugs were usually motionless on the inner walls of the holes and groups of huddling slugs were frequently present (Fig. 4). The exact number of slugs in a huddle

Figure 3. Two holes (arrows) in beech trees that were monitored between 2006 and 2024. **A, B**, first hole in February 2009 and November 2024, respectively. **C, D**, second hole in February 2009 and November 2024, respectively.

was sometimes difficult to count, because the slugs' bodies obscured each other. Some of the slugs had dipped the tips of their tails or the entire posterior halves of their bodies in the water present in the holes (Fig. 4).

Experimental results

The trunks of the beech trees in our study area were covered with a thin layer of algae and long, narrow, radula tracks winding through the algae layer could be seen on many trunks (Fig. 5A, B). Captive slugs that were given pieces of beech bark covered with algae fed on the algae and created similar tracks (Fig. 5C, D).

Captive slugs were often observed in huddles of 2–5 individuals in both dry and wet containers even when there was plenty of space for each slug to be away from others (Fig. 6A–C). Some huddles monitored during the day lasted up to about 7 hours while others were shorter lived. For

Figure 4. *Megapallifera mutabilis* huddling and tail-dipping in water-filled tree holes. **A**, a huddle of three slugs. Each slug was in contact with water. **B**, a huddle of five slugs with one separate slug at the top. **C**, four slugs in a tree hole. The foremost slug on the left wall was tail-dipping. **D**, a slug with the posterior half of its body in water. **E**, a composite image showing both ends of a water-filled tree hole. Slugs on the left were huddling, the slug on the right was tail-dipping.

example, in a container of three slugs that was monitored intermittently for 11 hours, a two-slug huddle lasted about 5 hours before dissociating; afterwards, the three slugs remained separate for about 2 hours before forming a three-

slug huddle at the end. The unpredictable behaviours of slugs and the somewhat transient nature of huddles did not allow us to determine whether slugs in dry containers were more likely to huddle than those in wet containers.

Figure 5. A, B, beech trees with radula tracks. C, captive *Megapallifera mutabilis* feeding on a piece of beech. Note the area behind the slug's tail from where the slug removed algae. D, feeding track created by another captive *M. mutabilis* on a piece of beech.

Figure 6. Captive *megapallifera mutabilis*. A–C, slugs huddling in high-humidity containers that had enough room for them to be separate from each other. D, E, a previously dehydrated slug with anterior body submerged in water. E, the same slug crawling fully submerged. F, a previously dehydrated slug tail-dipping.

During Experiment 1, 38 slugs were collected while they were climbing trees. In the laboratory they were placed either directly in water or on wet paper. The slugs were allowed to maintain contact with water for periods varying

from about 3 hours and 20 minutes to 6 hours and 45 minutes before each one was weighed again. Twenty-three of the slugs gained weight (range 0.7–80%; median 9.9%), while 15 slugs lost weight (–1.2% to –14.4%; median –4.3%) after

rehydration. There was a weak positive correlation between weight change and duration of water contact (Fig. 7A).

During Experiment 2, slugs were dehydrated in the laboratory and then placed in the presence of water. Seven slugs made voluntary contact with water for periods varying from about 15 minutes to 5 hours and 40 minutes. Dehydrated slugs usually entered the water headfirst, crawled fully or partially submerged for up to about 10 minutes, then emerged from the water but remained on the wall of the container usually dipping their tails in water (Fig. 6D–F). All seven slugs that contacted water during the rehydration period gained weight, while two slugs that avoided water continued to lose weight (Fig. 7B). Again, the results suggested a weak positive correlation between weight change and duration of water contact.

DISCUSSION

The propensity of *Megapallifera mutabilis* to climb “smooth-barked trees” has been noted before (Hubricht 1985). Paustian & Barbosa (2012) determined that in the deciduous forest habitats they studied *M. mutabilis* was much more common on live trees, including *F. grandifolia*, than on dead trees and woody debris. Our casual observations over the years have suggested that *M. mutabilis* may prefer beech trees, perhaps because of their relatively smooth trunks, to other trees. However, this may have been an observational bias, because the slugs were easier to spot on the lighter-coloured smooth barks of beech trees than on

the darker coloured rough barks of the other tree species. Besides *M. mutabilis*, we also observed on the trunks of beech trees other slug species, for example, *Arion subfuscus* (Draparnaud, 1805) and snails, including *Anguispira fergusonii* (Bland, 1862) and *Mesodon thyroideus* (Say, 1816). The radula tracks on the trunks of beech trees were undoubtedly created by the feeding of slugs, including *M. mutabilis*, and possibly snails on the algae covering the bark (Fig. 5A, B). This is supported by the creation of similar tracks by captive slugs in the laboratory (Fig. 5C, D). Paustian & Barbosa (2012) indeed showed, from analyses of fecal matter, that *M. mutabilis* consumed more algae than other types of food. Ingram (1941, 1949) also reported that *Philomycus carolinianus* (Bosc, 1802) preferred beech trees to hemlock trees (*Tsuga* species), noticed the presence of radula tracks on beech trees climbed by *P. carolinianus* and obtained radula tracks on algae-covered beech bark given to captive slugs.

Our laboratory studies involving the measurements of slug weights were complicated by two factors. First, slugs secreted mucus almost continuously, which causes considerable loss of water (Dainton 1954), and often excreted feces. Measurements of the weights of mucus and feces would have been impractical especially in containers with other items, such as wet paper and dishes of water into which slugs entered and exited while leaving mucus in the water. Therefore, we could not apply corrections to slugs’ weights to account for losses due to mucus and feces. We note that such losses were not taken into account in previous studies with slugs (Cook 1981; Prior 1984). Second, we could not

Figure 7. Weight changes of dehydrated slugs versus duration of hydration. **A**, 38 slugs collected while climbing trees (Experiment 1). Two pairs of data points were overlapping. **B**, nine slugs dehydrated in the laboratory (Experiment 2). Two slugs that did not contact water (open circles) were excluded from analysis. Blue broken lines indicate no change in weight; red lines are the ordinary least squares fit to the data. Statistics: r^2 , 0.02; p , 0.38 for A and r^2 , 0.10; p , 0.48 for B.

establish and follow a predetermined schedule of rehydration. This was because of the unpredictable behaviours of the slugs with respect to the duration of rehydration. This was noted before by Prior (1984) who showed that in *Limax maximus* Linnaeus, 1758 and *Ambigolimax valentianus* (A. Férussac, 1821) there was considerable variation in rehydration end points, that is when a slug stopped absorbing water. This variation was observed not only among individual slugs but also when the same individuals were tested repeatedly. Manipulating the slugs (to remove them from or to give them access to water) would probably have caused additional mucus loss. Despite these caveats, we believe that our results still allow us to make generalizations.

Our measurements showed that most slugs that had been feeding on trees gained weight after they were placed in contact with water (Fig. 7A). This indicated that slugs foraging on tree trunks were less than fully hydrated, probably mostly from water loss due to mucus excretion and evaporation through the skin. Our laboratory studies also showed that dehydrated slugs gained weight by being in contact with water for as short as 15 minutes and weight gain tended to increase with the duration of rehydration (Fig. 7B). We conclude that one reason why slugs enter water-filled tree holes is to rehydrate themselves. Tail-dipping as a natural rehydration behaviour of *M. mutabilis* is reported here for the first time. Dainton (1954) noted that *Deroceras reticulatum* (O.F. Müller, 1774), *Arion ater* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *L. maximus* can absorb water from damp paper or soil. In *L. maximus*, contact-rehydration (confusingly referred to as “drinking”) takes place through the sole (Prior 1984). Weight gain via bodily contact with water, including tail-dipping, indicates that *M. mutabilis* can also absorb water through its sole and perhaps also its integument. By keeping only their posterior bodies in water, but not their pneumostomes, the slugs are able to continue to breathe while absorbing water. In the laboratory we also observed dehydrated slugs submerging their entire bodies in water for brief periods (Fig. 6E). Matanock & Welsford (1995) demonstrated, by measuring hemolymph osmolalities, that individuals of *L. maximus* rehydrated themselves by entering and staying (mean ~20 min) in rain-water pools. Their and our observations suggest that rehydration in water may be a behaviour more common among slugs than occasional literature reports would suggest.

Huddling has previously been reported among the slug species in the Agriolimacidae (Binney 1851; Waite 1988), Limacidae (Binney 1851; Cook 1981), and Veronicellidae (Dundee *et al.* 1975). The behaviour has only been recorded incidentally in the Philomycidae. Binney (1851) noted that “no more than two” *Tebennophorus* (= *Philomycus*) could

usually be found together, Clapp (1920) reported a second-hand observation of huddling in *Philomycus rushi* Clapp, 1920, now *Pallifera ohioensis* (Sterki, 1916), and Webb (1950) briefly mentioned the huddling of *M. wetherbyi* in sandstone cavities. On the other hand, Pearce & Porter (2011) did not find statistically significant patterns of aggregation in groups of *P. carolinianus* in the laboratory. One confounding factor that may interfere with the interpretation of the results of huddling experiments is the dynamic nature of huddles. Pearce & Porter (2011) observed their slugs once a day for six days. However, as we noted above and as Cook (1981) emphasized, slugs may enter and leave a huddle frequently. Thus, frequent observations or continuous recording by camera (Cook 1981) would produce more reliable results than a single observation over many hours.

Our observations given here constitute the first detailed report of consistent huddling in a philomycid slug both in the wild and in the laboratory. The factors that promote the huddling of slugs are not known for certain. Pearce & Porter (2011) suggested that aggregation observed in nature may arise from the limited availability of suitable shelters. But we observed *M. mutabilis* huddle even when adequate space for each slug was available (Fig. 6A–C). It has been suggested that physical contact between two or more slugs decreases the exposed surface areas of slugs and thus reduces water loss through evaporation (Dundee *et al.* 1975; Cook 1981). However, *M. mutabilis* huddled even when water, and consequently high humidity, was present in their containers (Fig. 6A–C). Cook (1981) also observed that *Limacus maculatus* (Kaleniczenko, 1851) huddled when kept over water. Huddling may also have some sort of social function among conspecific slugs. For example, Cook (1981) showed that *L. maculatus* and *L. flavus* (Linnaeus, 1758) placed together formed mixed-species huddles but the percentage of animals participating in mixed-species huddles was less than in homogeneous huddles and that there was a tendency for a slug in a mixed-species huddle to be next to a member of the same species. This would suggest that phylogenetically distant slugs would avoid huddling with each other. However, a casual observation of prolonged physical contact between a *P. carolinianus* and an *A. subfuscus* is evidence, however trivial it may be, against that suggestion (Örstan 2007).

Our findings demonstrate the affinity of *M. mutabilis* to trees and water-filled holes. The lifespan of *M. mutabilis* in the wild is probably about one year (Örstan unpublished). Repeated observations of slugs in the two tree holes that we monitored over 18 years indicate that multiple generations used the same holes. Hiding in tree holes and tail-dipping appear to be adaptive behaviours that help *M. mutabilis*

regain lost water. The prevalence of tail-dipping in other philomycid species remains to be demonstrated.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Tim Pearce for reviewing an earlier draft and providing helpful comments and two reviewers for their comments that have improved the manuscript.

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Manuscript submitted: 27 April 2025

Revised Manuscript accepted: 10 October 2025

Editor: Robert Forsyth